

Building a Vertical Neutron Beamstop for the Reed Research Reactor

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ABSTRACT

The Reed Research Reactor has a neutron beam that utilizes the central thimble in a MARK I TRIGA reactor. It currently has no additional features to ensure experimenter and staff safety. A beamstop is in the process of construction to update the safety and utilization of the neutron beam facility. With a budget of \$300, this paper provides an affordable way to increase safety regarding neutron radiation. The neutron beamstop will be built by April 2026, per the graduation requirements of the author.

Keywords: NAA, neutron beam, beamstop

1. INTRODUCTION

The Reed Research Reactor (RRR) is a Mark I TRIGA Reactor based in Portland, Oregon, USA. This reactor design, seen in Fig. 1, has a hollow aluminum tube (the central thimble) extending from the center of the core to the top of the 25 ft pool, where there is a pedestrian bridge. When the tube is filled with nitrogen gas, it evacuates the existing water and creates a neutron beam. The current design assumes the neutrons that have traveled through the 20 ft of water are traveling straight up, and thus pose no danger to operators of the reactor or experimenters.

However, the current design has nothing to prevent the neutrons from traveling through the roof or preventing the irradiation of the air in the reactor room. Further, neutrons have been investigated more since the construction of the RRR in 1965. It is now common to have more safety features in place. This paper describes the creation of a beamstop to restrict the pathway of neutrons, limiting fields from Ar-41 and potential neutron doses.

2. PREVIOUS WORK

The RRR neutron beam facility has a mix of thermal and fast neutrons. [2] A lack of neutron detectors and higher dose reports from experimenters using the neutron beam caused the RRR to stop using this facility.

Neutron beam irradiations did not take place again for 12 years, until a simulation of the safety of the facility via TOols for PArtical Simulation (TOPAS) and experimental verification with powers less than 20 watts were performed. [3] Further tests conducted between 1 kW and 10 kW found the highest operating power of 230 kW (the internal limit of steady state operation) has a projected dose rate of 99.2 mSv/hr at the point where the central thimble meets the pedestrian bridge. [4] That would cause any radiation worker in the bay to exceed the limit of 250 mSv per year, mandated by Title 10 of the Code of Federal Regulations subsection 20 (10 CFR 20), in less than 3 hours. Since that puts experimenters at unnecessary risk, not following the tenants of ALARA (or ALARP), the RRR director will not allow further experiments to be performed using the neutron beam until a beamstop has been installed. There is an exception for running tests for the creation of a beamstop.

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Figure 1. Cutaway of a TRIGA reactor.[1] The "central experimental tube" is the "central thimble," and it extends to the gap between the control rod drives. An important difference about the RRR and this generic TRIGA cutaway is the control rod drives are in a triangular position, with the end of the central thimble in between them, as shown in Fig. 2.

3. CONSTRAINTS AND DESIGN

Creating a beamstop is the next step to revive the RRR neutron beam. The goal of the beamstop is to shield 99% of the neutron and gamma radiation. While safety is the driving force for the beamstop, there are many constraints to consider when creating its design.

The first constraint is that the neutron beam must be vertical. Due to the reactor pool being in-ground, it is not feasible to build any kind of horizontal neutron beam. Next, the control rod drive assemblies for the three control rods all surround the top of the central thimble on the bridge, as seen in Fig. 2, which necessitates that the beamstop be transportable to perform maintenance and limit interference

with daily operations. A lightweight material will help accomplish this.

Figure 2. Top down view of the control rod drives. The small circle in the middle of the rectangular cut out is the top of the central thimble (and neutron beam), and the three surrounding circles are the control rod drives.

There is also a large monetary constraint. The RRR does not have disposable funds, so the beamstop is funded by the Reed College Physics Department via the senior thesis funds. The cap on these funds is \$300. Due to the constraints, the design has a much smaller space for the samples to be irradiated than desired.

Hydrogenous materials can be a good neutron shield. [5] An inexpensive, lightweight, hydrogenous material is paraffin. To increase the neutron absorption, and decrease the thickness of material and gamma energies emitted, boron carbide powder can be mixed into the paraffin.

Figure 3. CAD model of the neutron beam stop. The model was designed in Autodesk's Fusion. There is a wooden table that supports the purely paraffin hemisphere, which is then engulfed by a 30% B_4C and 70% paraffin hemisphere with a section hollowed out for a sample. The surrounding tank will either hold water or be windled down to a single layer of aluminum to help with alpha and potentially gamma radiation.

The design is a set of concentric hemispheres with a portion hollowed out for the sample, as seen in Fig. 3. Because of the closeness of the control rod drives, the beamstop will be translated upward and given structural supports to remain upright. It will have an inner hemisphere with paraffin to moderate the neutrons, and then an outer hemisphere with boron carbide powder mixed with more paraffin to absorb the moderated neutrons. Presented in the figure 3, there is also an outer layer to help shield the incident radiation from boron and hydrogen interactions.

To determine the thickness, or radius, of the paraffin hemispheres, a series of tests will be conducted in spring of 2026. A variety of thicknesses and concentrations between 30 and 50 percent of B_4C by weight will be cast into small pucks that cover the top of the neutron beam. Pure gold foils will be placed on the bottom and top of the puck, irradiated at 10 kW, and analyzed with NAA to determine the shielding efficiency of each thickness at each concentration.

4. MATERIAL AND THICKNESS TESTING

Test pieces comprising of cylinders with a 60 mm diameter and varying heights were created by mixing 30% (by weight) boron carbide (B_4C) powder and 70% paraffin (with a melting point of 344 K), heating it to about 358 K, then casting it from a mold. To keep the mixture from separating, it was slowly spun while it cooled, which resulted in a slightly uneven edge. The test pieces extruding 25 mm, 65 mm, 105 mm, and 145 mm were propped up by lead bricks and placed in the Oregon State test reactor's (OSTR) neutron beam, for 120 seconds each, between a gold foil, shown in Fig. 4. A control with 0 mm of shielding was also run.

Figure 4. Test piece (25 mm) in neutron beam. The neutrons are coming in from the right side of the image. The gold flux foil is suspended in the plastic bag, aligned with the center of the test piece.

5. RESULTS

Using neutron activation analysis (NAA), the foils provided activities in Becquerels (Bq). The foil from the unshielded control test provided a baseline activity per mass of 330 Bq/g. The rest of the foils, with test pieces of various thicknesses shielding them from the neutron beam, were given a shielding efficiency in comparison to the control. The different heights of the test pieces did not vary in shielding efficiency beyond 1%, as seen in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. The shielding efficiency of the 30% B_4C test pieces versus their heights (thicknesses). The average efficiency of the pieces, excluding the 0 point, is 95%.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A neutron beamstop is necessary to safely resume operating the RRR neutron beam. The vertical orientation of the neutron beam provides unique challenges in building its beamstop. Further tests need to take place to create a curve and find the minimum thickness of the material. It appears that the current heights of the test pieces max out the shielding efficiency. Unfortunately, 95% of 9920 mSv/hr will still maintain the reactor bay a radiation area per the 10 CFR 20. Further design choices or an operational limit need to be considered before implementing the neutron beamstop.

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